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Bio-efficacy of biorational insecticides against thrips and aphids on pomegranate and their safety to natural enemies

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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted at the Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Bengaluru, during 2015-16 to study the bio-efficacy of biorational insecticides viz., Azadirachtin (1000 ppm), *Lecanicillium lecanii* (2x10⁸ spores/g), Neem soap (@ 10 g/l), Organic salt 30 WS, Organic salt 30 WS, Spinosad 45 SC and Dimethoate 30 EC against pomegranate thrips (*Scirtothrips dorsalis* Hood) and aphids (*Aphis punicae* Passerini) and safety on natural enemies (*Coccinella transversalis*). The results revealed that all the insecticidal treatments were observed to be effective in reducing thrips and aphid infestation on pomegranate crop. Among the evaluated insecticides, the treatment with Spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l was found to be significantly superior in recording a minimum population of thrips (0.92 thrips/three leaves) and aphids (7.54 aphids/three leaves) respectively. However organic salt and spinosad were found to be more safest chemicals to the coccinellid beetles.

Keywords: biorationals, bio-efficacy, sucking pests, organic salt

1. Introduction

Pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.) is an important fruit crop of arid and semiarid regions in the world. On pomegranate different sucking pests namely aphid, thrips, whiteflies, mealy bugs, scale insects and mites were considered as minor pests earlier but in recent years, they assumed as a major pest status, which results in reduction of plant vigour, quality and fruit yield of pomegranate (Balikai *et al.*, 2009) ^[1]. Karuppuchamy (1994) ^[2] recorded insect pests attacking pomegranate along with plant part infested, peak activity and their natural enemies in Tamil Nadu. Balikai (2000) ^[3] enlisted 32 insect pests of which nine were sucking pests and found feeding on pomegranate in the districts of Bijapur and Bagalkot of Karnataka. Among different sucking pests, thrips (*Scirtothrips dorsalis* Hood) and pomegranate aphid (*Aphis punicae* Passerini) were considered as major sucking pests (Wadhi and Batra, 1969) ^[4]. Sreedevi and Verghese (2009) ^[5] observed the significant flower and immature fruit drop due to infestation of aphids.

A. punicae was found infesting severely to twigs, leaves, flower buds, flowers and fruits by desapping, which resulted in loss of quality of fruits and reduction in fruit yield at central Maharashtra (Mote *et al.*, 1992) ^[6], in Tamil Nadu (Karuppuchamy *et al.*, 1998) ^[7] and in Karnataka (Biradar and Shaila, 2004) ^[8]. The *A. punicae* was considered as a serious pest that invaded pomegranate orchards in the spring season in most years and sometimes at the beginning of the summer in Eastern Turkey (Bayhan *et al.*, 2005) ^[9].

Two species of thrips viz., *Retithrips syriacus* (Munae) and *Rhipiphorotherips cruentatus* Hood have been reported on pomegranate by Ananthkrishnan (1971) ^[10]. Besides pomegranate, these two species of thrips have been also recorded on jamun, castor, rose (Butani, 1976) ^[11], is assuming a status of key pest on pomegranate under the semi-arid conditions in Gujarat (Bagle, 1993) ^[12]. According to Everly (1960) ^[13], heavy rains reduced the population of thrips while, hot and dry conditions with temperature above 37.8°C favoured the multiplication of thrips. The peak infestation of the grape vine thrips was noticed during May-June in South India and March-April and August to October in Haryana and Punjab (Butani, 1974) ^[14].

Karuppuchamy (1994) ^[15] recorded *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) and *Scymnus coccivora* Ayyar on pomegranate aphid, *A. punicae*. Mani and Krishnamoorthy (1995) ^[16] reported that, *A. punicae* was preyed by three coccinellids namely *Scymnus castaneus* Sci., *S. latemaculata*

parasitoids have been recorded on aphids. Amin (2002) [17] collected twelve species of natural enemies from the colonies of pomegranate aphid *A. punicae* in the El-Beida region, Libya, including eleven species of predators, seven species belonged to the family Coccinellidae and one species each to the families Anthocoridae, Syrphidae, Cecidomyiidae and Chrysopidae, in addition to a parasitoid wasp of the family Braconidae.

Mote *et al.* (1993) [18] reported that dimethoate (0.03%) and methyl demeton (0.03%) caused over 90 per cent mortality of pomegranate aphids. Karuppuchamy *et al.* (1998) [19] found the sprays of phosalone, endosulfan at 0.07%, neem oil 3%, fish oil rosin soap 2.5% to be highly effective by causing cent per cent mortality of aphids at three days after insecticide treatment on pomegranate. According to Verghese (2000) [20], various neem extracts and *Pongamia pinnata* oil did not have sufficient potential to achieve a rapid knockdown effect on *A. punicae* on pomegranate and were significantly inferior to phosphamidon. Imidacloprid (0.5 ml/l) and dimethoate (1.7 ml/l) were found to be highly effective and consistent in reducing aphid population over 50 per cent at 15 days after treatment. Maximum yield of 44.63 and 38.25t/ha of pomegranate fruits was obtained in imidacloprid and dimethoate treatments, respectively. With this background, an experiment was planned and designed to know the bio-efficacy of different biorational insecticides against thrips and aphids in pomegranate and its safety to major natural enemies.

2. Materials and Methods

Field experiments were carried out for the management of sucking pests on pomegranate at Division of Entomology and Nematology, ICAR-Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Bengaluru (11.294° N latitude & 75.82° E longitude, and 915 m above mean sea level) with an established pomegranate orchard (variety Bhagawa), which was well maintained by following the all recommended package of practices. (IIHR, 2015). The experiment was laid out with eight treatments replicated thrice in Randomized Block Design (RCBD).

The biorationals insecticides *viz.*, Azadirachtin 10,000 ppm @ 1 ml/l, *Lecanicillium lecanii* (2x10⁸ spores/g) @5 ml/l, Neem soap @ 10 g/l, Organic salt 30 WS @ 4 ml/l, Organic salt 30 WS @ 5 ml/l, Spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l and Dimethoate 30 EC @ 1.6 ml/l as standard check were used as treatments for

the experiment. Treatments were imposed when the thrips and aphid population reached above economic threshold level (ETL) at the vegetative crop growth period during 2015-16. Total two sprays of different treatments were given using a knapsack high volume sprayer during morning hours at 15 days intervals. Observations on aphid population was recorded on randomly selected three young leader shoots (5cm) and number of thrips was counted from top three leaves on 15 randomly selected and labeled plants at a day before spray (DBS), three, seven and 15 days after each spray. Later, mean number of insects from two sprays and also pooled mean was calculated. The data regarding to above insecticides evaluated by using WSP statistical software.

3. Results and Discussion

Data recorded on population of major sucking pests namely, *S. dorsalis* and *A. punicae* on pomegranate at different days after treatments are presented under different subheadings below:

3.1 Thrips (*Scirtothrips dorsalis*)

Day before initiation of spraying showed that there was uniform distribution of thrips in the plots. The results revealed that (Table.1) all the treatments were significantly found superior over the control. Among the different insecticides, spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l recorded significantly lowest (1.32 and 0.51 thrips/three leaves) thrips population after first, second spray during the experimental period against pomegranate thrips. The next best treatment was, dimethoate 30 EC @ 1.6 ml/l, organic salt 30 WS @ 5 ml/l and azadirachtin 10,000 ppm @ 1ml/l. Whereas, control and neem soap @ 10 g/l (9.46 and 3.23 thrips/three leaves) found to be least effective in reducing the thrips population in both first and second spray. The present findings are agreement with those of (Anon., 2009) [21] spinosad 2.5 SC at 75 g a.i./ ha treatment was found to be most effective treatment for the control of thrips (*S. dorsalis*) in pomegranate.

3.2 Aphids (*Aphis punicae*)

The population of aphids ranged at a day before spray indicating uniform distribution and it differ non significantly among the different treatments.

Table 1: Bio-efficacy of biorational insecticides against thrips, *Scirtothrips dorsalis* on pomegranate

Treatments	Mean no. of thrips/three leaves (n=15 plants)										Pooled mean
	I Spray					II Spray					
	DBS	3 DAS	7 DAS	15 DAS	Mean	DBS	3 DAS	7 DAS	15 DAS	Mean	
T1 -Azadirachtin (10,000 ppm) @ 1 ml/l	9.30 (3.13)	2.33 (1.68)	2.22 (1.65)	2.41 (1.71)	2.32	8.36 (2.98)	2.57 (1.74)	2.22 (1.65)	1.83 (1.53)	2.20	2.26
T2 - <i>Lecanicillium lecanii</i> @ 2 g/l	8.96 (3.07)	2.61 (1.76)	2.54 (1.74)	2.57 (1.75)	2.57	8.42 (2.99)	2.92 (1.85)	2.53 (1.74)	2.68 (1.78)	2.71	2.64
T3 -Neem soap @ 10 g/l	8.53 (3.00)	3.23 (1.93)	3.15 (1.91)	3.32 (1.95)	3.23	8.37 (2.98)	3.38 (1.97)	3.10 (1.90)	3.21 (1.92)	3.23	3.23
T4 -Organic salt 30 WS @ 4 ml/l	9.11 (3.10)	2.97 (1.86)	2.57 (1.74)	2.72 (1.79)	2.75	8.52 (2.99)	3.10 (1.90)	2.80 (1.82)	2.96 (1.85)	2.95	2.85
T5 -Organic salt 30 WS @ 5 ml/l	8.95 (3.07)	2.14 (1.62)	2.05 (1.60)	2.37 (1.70)	2.30	8.79 (3.05)	2.11 (1.620)	2.08 (1.60)	2.33 (1.68)	2.17	2.24
T6 -Spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l	9.24 (3.12)	1.67 (1.47)	1.36 (1.36)	0.95 (1.20)	1.32	8.30 (2.97)	1.24 (1.32)	0.22 (0.85)	0.07 (0.75)	0.51	0.92
T7 -Dimethoate 30 EC @ 1.6 ml/l	9.37 (3.14)	1.81 (1.52)	1.76 (1.50)	1.57 (1.44)	1.71	8.43 (2.99)	1.93 (1.55)	1.78 (1.51)	1.76 (1.50)	1.82	1.77
T8 -Untreated control	9.27 (3.13)	9.38 (3.14)	9.51 (3.16)	9.74 (3.20)	9.54	8.97 (3.08)	9.22 (3.12)	9.33 (3.14)	9.57 (3.17)	9.37	9.46
SEM±	-	0.11	0.20	0.12	-	-	0.20	0.10	0.18	-	-

CD at 5%	NS	0.35	0.63	0.38	-	NS	0.61	0.33	0.54	-	-
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DBS - Day before spraying, DAS - Days after spraying Figures in parentheses are $\sqrt{x+0.5}$ transformed values

Table 2: Bio-efficacy of bio rational insecticides against aphid, *Aphis punicae* on pomegranate

Treatments	Mean no. of aphids /three shoots (n=15 plants)										Pooled mean
	I Spray					II Spray					
	DBS	3 DAS	7 DAS	15 DAS	Mean	DBS	3 DAS	7 DAS	15 DAS	Mean	
T1 -Azadirachtin (10,000 ppm) @ 1 ml/l	30.50 (5.57)	16.52 (4.12)	10.55 (3.32)	10.89 (3.37)	12.65	28.84 (5.41)	13.35 (3.72)	10.30 (3.29)	10.62 (3.33)	11.42	12.03
T2 - <i>Lecanicillium lecanii</i> @ 2 g/l	31.74 (5.68)	18.47 (4.36)	13.01 (3.67)	14.56 (3.88)	15.35	31.74 (5.68)	14.72 (3.90)	13.25 (3.71)	13.66 (3.76)	13.87	14.61
T3 -Neem soap @ 10 g/l	33.44 (5.83)	19.51 (4.47)	14.55 (3.88)	15.45 (3.99)	16.50	34.45 (5.91)	16.29 (4.10)	15.16 (3.96)	15.65 (4.02)	15.70	16.10
T4 -Organic salt 30 WS @ 4 ml/l	33.61 (5.84)	19.67 (4.49)	15.23 (3.96)	15.86 (4.04)	16.92	30.74 (5.59)	17.33 (4.22)	14.34 (3.85)	14.81 (3.91)	15.49	8.39
T5 -Organic salt 30 WS @ 5 ml/l	34.41 (5.91)	18.20 (4.32)	9.77 (3.20)	10.51 (3.32)	12.82	30.50 (5.57)	13.77 (3.78)	11.34 (3.440)	11.98 (3.53)	12.36	12.59
T6 -Spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l	30.74 (5.59)	12.13 (3.55)	7.29 (2.79)	6.06 (2.56)	8.49	28.93 (5.42)	10.52 (3.32)	5.57 (2.45)	3.68 (2.04)	6.59	7.54
T7 -Dimethoate 30 EC @ 1.6 ml/l	36.26 (6.06)	15.23 (3.97)	9.75 (3.20)	9.14 (3.10)	11.37	31.39 (5.60)	13.08 (3.69)	8.36 (2.98)	8.15 (2.94)	9.86	10.61
T8 -Untreated control	31.04 (5.59)	32.89 (5.77)	35.90 (6.03)	39.85 (6.35)	36.21	29.33 (5.45)	30.77 (5.59)	32.05 (5.71)	35.07 (5.96)	32.63	34.42
SEM±	-	0.11	0.20	0.12	-	-	0.20	0.10	0.16	-	-
CD at 5%	NS	0.35	0.63	0.38	-	NS	0.61	0.33	0.49	-	-

DBS - Day before spraying, DAS - Days after spraying

Figures in parentheses are $\sqrt{x+0.5}$ transformed values

All the treatments were found to be significantly superior in reducing the aphid population as compared to untreated control. spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l found to be effective in reducing the aphids population. Dimethoate 30 EC @ 1.6 ml/l and azadirachtin 10,000 ppm @ 1 ml/l and *Lecanicillium lecanii* @ 2 g/l were recorded to be the next best treatments in reducing aphid after first spray.

In case of after second spray. Spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l recorded a minimum number of aphid population (10.52 aphids/three shoots). Whereas, dimethoate 30 EC @ 1.6 ml/l recorded 13.08 aphids/three shoots which was on par with azadirachtin 10,000 ppm @ 1ml/l (13.35 aphids/three shoots) (Table 2). Least number of aphid populations (5.57

aphids/three shoots) was observed with spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l after seven days of the spray. Similar trend was observed at 15 days after spraying with 3.68 aphids/three shoots from spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l treated plot.

The overall mean population differed significantly among treatments with respect to number of aphids per three shoots. Among the different treatments spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l (7.54 aphids/three shoots) was significantly superior to all the other treatments (Table 2). The highest population was recorded in neem soap @ 10 g/l (16.10 aphids/three shoots) followed by *L. lecanii* @ 2 g/l (14.61 aphids/three shoots), organic salt 30 WS @ 5 ml/l (12.59 aphids/three shoots respectively.

Table 3: Safety of different biorational insecticides against coccinellid, *Coccinella transversalis* on pomegranate

Treatments	Mean no. of coccinellids/three shoots (n=15 plants)										Pooled mean
	I Spray					II Spray					
	DBS	3 DAS	7 DAS	15 DAS	Mean	DBS	3 DAS	7 DAS	15 DAS	Mean	
T1 -Azadirachtin (10,000 ppm) @ 1 ml/l	6.21 (2.59)	2.21 (1.63)	1.79 (1.51)	1.94 (1.56)	1.98	5.16 (2.38)	1.74 (1.49)	1.37 (1.37)	1.44 (1.39)	1.52	1.75
T2 - <i>Lecanicillium lecanii</i> @ 2 g/l	5.99 (2.55)	2.87 (1.84)	2.63 (1.77)	2.75 (1.80)	2.75	5.18 (2.38)	2.56 (1.75)	2.36 (1.69)	2.40 (1.70)	2.44	2.60
T3 -Neem soap @ 10 g/l	6.04 (2.56)	2.50 (1.73)	2.47 (1.72)	2.59 (1.76)	2.52	5.43 (2.44)	2.26 (1.66)	2.11 (1.62)	2.35 (1.69)	2.24	2.38
T4 -Organic salt 30 WS @ 4 ml/l	5.80 (2.51)	3.16 (1.91)	2.69 (1.78)	2.80 (1.82)	2.88	5.31 (2.41)	2.74 (1.80)	2.60 (1.76)	2.86 (1.83)	2.73	2.81
T5 -Organic salt 30 WS @ 5 ml/l	5.66 (2.48)	3.09 (1.90)	2.62 (1.77)	3.06 (1.89)	2.92	5.28 (2.40)	2.68 (1.78)	2.51 (1.73)	2.65 (1.77)	2.61	2.77
T6 -Spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l	5.89 (2.53)	2.93 (1.85)	2.48 (1.71)	2.58 (1.76)	2.66	5.09 (2.36)	2.59 (1.76)	2.73 (1.79)	2.86 (1.83)	2.73	2.70
T7 -Dimethoate 30 EC @ 1.6 ml/l	5.94 (2.54)	0.66 (1.04)	0.19 (0.83)	0.32 (0.90)	0.39	5.18 (2.38)	1.09 (1.25)	0.53 (1.02)	0.41 (0.95)	0.68	0.53
T8 -Untreated control	5.78 (2.50)	5.77 (2.50)	5.89 (2.53)	6.14 (2.58)	5.93	5.22 (2.39)	5.36 (2.42)	5.50 (2.45)	5.79 (2.51)	5.55	5.74
SEM±	-	0.21	0.19	0.07	-	-	0.16	0.10	0.09	-	-
CD at 5%	NS	0.65	0.58	0.22	-	NS	0.51	0.30	0.30	-	-

DBS - Day before spraying, DAS - Days after spraying

Figures in parentheses are $\sqrt{x+0.5}$ transformed values

3.3 Safety on *Coccinella transversalis*

Initially the natural enemy population was uniform in all the treatments but after the first spray there was a significant difference among the biorationals. (Table 3). The mean pooled data of two sprays revealed that the least population of coccinellids (0.53 coccinellids/three shoots) was recorded in dimethoate 30 EC @ 1.6 ml/l treated plot area followed by azadirachtin 10,000 @ 1.0 ml/l (1.75 coccinellids/three shoots) and neem soap @ 10 g/l (2.38 coccinellids/three shoots), respectively. The highest lady bird beetle population was observed in the organic salt 30 WS (@ 4 ml/l & 5 ml/l) (2.81 and 2.77 /three shoots) spinosad 45 SC@ 0.2 ml/l (2.70/ three shoots) and *Lecanicillium lecanii* @ 2 g/l (2.60/ three shoots) treated plots respectively. The present findings are in close agreement with findings of Mollah *et al.* (2012) [22] and Anjumoni *et al.* (2011) [23] who also reported that dimethoate was highly toxic to Coccinellid beetles.

4. Conclusion

The result revealed that all the selected bio-pesticides treatments spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l was found significantly superior in reducing thrips and aphid population, where as in order of safety to coccinellid predators was observed in organic salt 30 WS (@ 4 ml/l and 5 ml/l), spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l and *Lecanicillium lecanii* @ 2 g/l respectively.

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